

THERMODYNAMICS AND INSTABILITY OF DIELECTRIC ELASTOMER

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Abstract

Dielectric elastomers (DEs), a type of electroactive polymer (EAP). The acrylic acid and silicone are common dielectric elastomer materials. Subject to a voltage through its thickness, a membrane of a dielectric elastomer reduces thickness and enlarges area. It was discovered a decade ago that an applied voltage may cause dielectric elastomers to strain over 100% [1]. Because of this large strain, dielectric elastomers are often called artificial muscles. In addition to large voltage-induced strains, other desirable attributes of dielectric elastomers include fast response, high energy density, no noise, light weight, high efficiency and high responsive speed and low cost. This electromechanical coupling is being studied intensely for diverse applications, including soft robots, adaptive optics, Braille display medical devices, and electric generators. The research on dielectric elastomers' failure, large deformation and nonlinear electromechanical stability is an interesting topic in recent years [2-5]. Recently, a lot of research work focused on either large deformation or electromechanical stability has been carried out.

Zhao and Suo proposed a theoretical method to investigate the electromechanical instability of ideal dielectric elastomers [5]. In the statement of this theory, other researchers started to investigate the electromechanical stability of various types of dielectric elastomer combining the strain energy function for hyperelastic materials such as Ogden model, Neo-Hookean model, Arruda-Boyce model and Mooney-Rivlin model. From these researches, the relations among the nominal stress, the pre-stretch, the nominal electric displacement and the nominal electric field were described accurately. In the above-mentioned theoretical study of dielectric elastomers, linear electrostatic free energy has been employed to characterize the polarization, actuation and instability. This linearity is applicable previously because the conventional dielectric elastomer is susceptible to electromechanical instability, a constant voltage squeezing the elastomer, resulting in a higher electric field and hence ceaselessly thinning the film until failure, and the polarization at electromechanical instability still resides within the linear regime.

In this paper, we first introduce the constitutive theory of dielectric elastomer under electromechanical coupling fields. Thermodynamics gives

$$s_1 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_1} \quad (1)$$

$$s_2 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_2} \quad (2)$$

$$s_3 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_3} \quad (3)$$

$$E^- = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial D^-} \quad (4)$$

Once a specific free energy is given, we obtain the state of dielectric elastomer under voltage and voltage.

Then, a free energy function which consists of nonlinear elastic strain energy and nonlinear electric field energy is proposed to construct the constitutive equation and predicate the electromechanical

instability and the snap-through instability of dielectric elastomer undergoing polarization saturation. The free energy function contains

$$U(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = -\frac{\mu}{2} J_{\text{lim}} \log \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2} - 3}{J_{\text{lim}}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$V(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, D^-) = \frac{D_s D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1}}{2\varepsilon} \log \left(\frac{1 + D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}{1 - D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s} \right) + \frac{D_s^2}{2\varepsilon} \log \left(1 - \frac{D_s^{-2} \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}}{D_s^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

Consider the unequal-biaxial condition of dielectric elastomer, $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda$, we get that

$$\frac{s}{\mu} = \frac{2J_{\text{lim}}}{J_{\text{lim}} - (2\lambda^2 + \lambda^{-4} - 3)} (\lambda - \lambda^{-5}) - \frac{2D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \left[\frac{\exp(2 \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda^2 / \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}) - 1}{\exp(2 \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda^2 / \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}) + 1} \right] \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda \quad (7)$$

The voltage-stretch curve with different extension limit is showed in Figure 1. When J_{lim} and $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}$ are both small, the nominal electric field increases monotonously with the stretch, avoiding local maximum value and the dielectric elastomer can approach its stable state. When $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon} \rightarrow \infty$ and J_{lim} is a finite value, the nominal electric field attains the local maximum value first. Then, the dielectric elastomer goes through the snap instability with the voltage increasing. When $J_{\text{lim}} \rightarrow \infty$ and $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon} \rightarrow \infty$, the dielectric elastomer undergoes the pull-in electromechanical instability. Therefore, to get a large deformation, the applied voltage should achieve two limits, lower than the breakdown voltage of the material, and approaching the voltage undergoing the snap instability.

Fig. 1. Consider the effect of the strain-stiffening, nominal electric field and stretch of dielectric elastomer undergoing polarization saturation under the loading condition $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda$.

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